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LAWRENCE HERTZEG – RECORD ON THE ATTACK AT THE DJAKOVSKA VINERY

Abstract: In the transcription and translation of an archival document from the Historical archive of Sombor the legal case of the Lawrence Hertzeg (Laurentus Hertzeg), a Jew from the city of Sombor who was attacked and beaten on the July 17th 1808, is brought to light. His case is of a great importance as it's very well documented and it shows us the procedure that was followed in the cases similar to the attack that happened to Lawrence Hertzeg. Document follows medical report, specification of the costs and testimonies of the witnesses.

Keywords: Jews, Vojvodina, violence, Sombor

Non MeSH: Sombor, medical report, authorities, Lawrence Hertzeg (Laurentus Hertzeg)

Jews have been living on the Balkan Peninsula for almost 2000 years. [1 p7] However, their remnants from the times of Roman and Byzantine Empires are only preserved in traces. Various archaeological finds corroborate their presence in towns on Adriatic coast; also, some surnames that remain today could be traced to those early Jewish communities, such as *Papo* or *Romano*. [1 p7] If we observe their existence on the territory of modern Vojvodina, there are no traces of larger Jewish presence before the arrival of the Ottomans. [1 p8] However, the larger influx of Jewish settlers in Vojvodina happened during the Habsburg rule (1699-1918), especially after 1726. The main reason for that was the *Familiatengesetz*, the law that allowed marriage only to one man from a Jewish family within the provinces of the Holy Roman Empire of the German Nation. Therefore, a great number of younger Jewish men and women migrated to Vojvodina, in order to escape the limitations imposed by the law. [1 p11-4]

The relation of authorities and government toward Jews in decades after 1726 was variable. It ranged from reluctant tolerance to a more repressive bearing, which encompassed relocation to specific quarters within a city as well as ban on practicing of certain trades (goldsmith, soap-making etc). However, it could be argued that their condition somewhat improved during the reign of Emperor Joseph II (1780-1790) and subsequent rulers. On the other hand, it should be noted that their position worsened during times of war, social upheavals and revolutions. [1 p21-6]

In this paper, we will present a transcription and translation of an archival document from the Historical archive of Sombor, [2] which could provide an insight into relation of non-Jewish population towards Jews and their interaction, as well as the relation and response of authorities when those interactions took a more violent turn. It should be noted that, at the present state of research, we are unable to provide the complete picture of the incident. We only know that a Jew named Lawrence Hertzeg (Laurentus Hertzeg) from the city of Sombor was attacked and beaten on the July 17th 1808 near the winery „Djakovska“, on the road connecting Sombor and Baja, by Nikola and George Fratric (Nicolaum ac Georgium ambos Fratric), and two local men named Augustin Rados (Augustinus Radoss) and George Jozic (Georgius Jozits). From the testimony of witnesses it could only be concluded that the attack had indeed taken place, however we don't know all the circumstances. One of the witnesses (Martin Fratrić declared that there was a verbal exchange between Hertzeg and the defendants, which was followed by violence. Hertzeg himself said before the Magistrate that he met four above mentioned men near the winery „Djakovska“; because he was unacquainted with them, he redirected his cart on the side of the road - out of decency and to avoid any altercation. However, they started hurling insults and attacked him. The authorities decided to conduct further investigation, and senators Nikola Simic (Nicolaus Simits) and George Sljivic (Georgius Sztrilich) were tasked to examine other witnesses. Unfortunately, we don't know how the investigation was concluded. The last information in the document is dated on August 8th 1808, and it notes that the investigation is still ongoing.

The importance of this document is in the fact that the entire case is very well documented and also covered with detail medical record of the condition of the victim – Lawrence Herzog. It also gives us better idea of the legal system in Sombor but also the costs of the surgeon, attorney, traveling, value of goods etc.

Transcript

Specificatio

Cure chirurgica Judei Laurentii Hertzeg gremialis inhabitatoris, ut sequitur

f x

1. Pro viso reperto 2f
2. A 19^a Julii usque 6^{em} augusti a.c. 38 visitas ei prestiti, singulam visitam a 36x computando facit 20f
3. Pro necessariis medicamentis 6f 51x

Summa 28 f 51x

Sigilatum Sombor die 12^a aug. 1808

Josephus Oravec

Ord Civitatis chirurgus

Specificatio cure chirurgica Judei Laurentii Hertzeg

Specificum

Expensarum per infrascriptum in sui curam habitatum et quidem 33f in argentea pecunia penes se habitos qui periverunt in moderno pretio assumpti facit – 66f

Para Chyrurgo pro medicamentis soluti – 3f 4x

Pro vectura homini cuidam Zomborinum usque soluti – 2f

Tunicam brevem ex Lacerarunt et inusuabilem reddiderunt pro qua computantque – 10f

Pro ternis advocacionibus illos Huszaroni voluti – 3f

Chyrurgo pro cura et ad apotecam pro medicamentis soluti – 28f 51x

Cancellista pro opposite specific presenti – 1f

Summa ----- 113f 55x

Positio 1^a limita ad 33f -----33f

80f 55x

Laurentus Hertzeg, Judaus gremialis

Sigilatum Zombori 12^a Augusti 1808.

Visum repertum

Super Judao Laurentio Hertzeg inhabitatore Zomboriensi die 19^a Julii 1808. In sequenti statu valetudinario reperi; ut sequitur

1. Dexterata pars faciei lasionem cutaneam unius, a medii pollicis longam, probabilius unguibus factam passu est.
2. In sinistra parte Maxilla inferioris depillatio barbe apparebat

3. In dextera parte colli sex ^{no} lasiones cutana sanguine suffuse, ita censeo ungvibus facta reperta sunt.
4. Sinister humerus luxationem passus est, preterea duo ^{no} signa contusionum cum tumore, et decussione cutis duorum pollicum in latitudine, cum tendinum lasione videbantur.
5. Sinistra Clavicula duo ^{no} contusiones accepit.
6. Supradictus patiens contra pectoris dolores, et contra grave respirium mihi conquestus.

Quod luxationem brachii sinistri ego non reposuerim, de eo sum certus veram luxationem brachii habuisse, qua per chirurgum Garenssem die 17. Julii reposita est. Qua fidedigne Amplissimo Juditio humillime refero.
Sigilatam Zomborini die 19. Julii 1808.
Josephus Oravec
Ord. chirurgus civitatis Zombor
Visum repertum Judai Laurentii Hertzeg

Investigatio

Intuitu aggresionis ac verberationis Laurenti Herczegh Judao hujati in via Bajam ducente, non procul a Civico educilli Gacoviensi dictum, per Nicolaum ac Georgium ambos Fratricis, nec non Augustinum Radoss, atque Georgium Jozits omnes gremiales. Die 17. Julii 1808. illata, per nos infrascriptus facta

Primus Michael Fratricis fassus est quod prenomina die cum Nicolao et Georgio Fratricis, item Augustino Radoss, nec non Georgio Jozis in educillo Gacoviensi dicto recreationis causa cum liripio existentes ad allodia domum dum reverses fuisset, ob immenses febres semet male valere sentiens, pro suis consociis domum ad allodia abeundo non indexit, qualiter eius consocii Judaum Laurentium Herczegh aggradiendo verberaverint; at sibi notum sit, quod ipsissime die ad vespere et eius consociis duo quippe Nicolaus et Georgius Fratricis testem accedendo testi sequentiali his formaliter Naraverim: darzi bio darzi vidio, kako izmo Cifutinu bradu iscupali (da si bio, da si video kako smo Čifutinu bradu išcupali) de reliquo nihil.

Secundus Martinus Fratricis detexit, quod idem a loco agresionis non procul constitutus vident quailter Judaus proprimis pronuncinatis videlicet aggresori.... Devia-verit, illi vero eo non obstante Judaum aggradiendo telyiga.... rotas Capiendo eundem Judaum e teljiga evertare voluerint, scique luctando ad terram Detracerint, de neque Augustinus Nadoss eundem Judaum per barbam coceperit. De reliquo nihil. Testius

Species – Facti

Intuitu aggresionis ac verberationis Laurentio Herczeg Judao gremiali, in via Bajam ducente, non procul a Civico educillo Gacoviensi nuncupato, per Nicolaum et Georgium ambos Fratricis, nec non Augustinum Radoss, atque Georgium Jozits omnes gremiales, die 17. Julii 1808. Illata; et quidem:

Laurentius Herczegh intuit aggressionis, ac verberationis per Nicolaum ac Georgium Fratricis, item Augustinum Radoss, nec non Georgium Jozits eidem illato coram nobis Magistratualiter Commissionatis detexit: quod idem die 17. Julii 1808 propria teljiga ad nundines Bajenses pacifice profectus, et non procul a Civico Educillo Gakoviensi nuncupato in publice via constitutus viderit preexpositos 4 inhabitatores hujates pro tum sibi de cognominibus ignotos, Liripipio ludentes, ex parte Gakoviensis Educilli versus allodia redeuntes, praeter condecientiam ob majorem ini haustum latos, videndoque ob amorem pacis ipsis sue teljige a procul deviaerit, illi vero non considerate hacce per eundem Judaum facta deviatione, inter blasphemias primo rotas talyiga capiendo telyigam invertere, ipsumque Judaum e talyiga ejicere voluerint subseque e telyiga ad terram detractum per vestem capiendo traxerint complures ictus corpora eiusdem intulerint trahendoque Manum sinistram luxaverint, imo per barbam eius barbe capillarum cum excusione coeperint, hacque occasione taliter per eosdem aggressus fecisset, idem Judaus penes se habitos in argento 32 florenos perdiderit, denique prenominati aggressors Judaum, du mille Zomborinum reverti coactus fecisset ac redere voluisset eatenus querelam deponendi gratia, Zomborinum redire non admiseret, verum eundem

Extractus Protocolli

Judao gremiali Laurentio Herczegh ob sui per Nicolaum et Georgium ambos Fratricis, nec non Augustinum Radoss atque Georgium Jozits in via Bajam ducente protensive faceram aggressionem et verberationem querulante

Determinatum est: Dominis senatoribus Nicolao Simits et Georgio Sztivlits pro investigatione exmissis auditis Testibus oralem Relationem prestantibus siquidem pro uberiori eruditione plures Testes exaudiendi forent incarceratos quidem erga Fidejussionales Domini senatoris Mathia Jozits, Thoma Radoss, Marci Fratricis dimitti ulteriorem vero investigationem Dominis praeexmissis senatoribus Relationem facturis committi: In Senatu Zomboriensi dei 25 Julii 1808. Celebrato.

Extradare per Emericum Bossnyak
Jur. Civitatis vicenotarius

Infrascripti penes hic sub advolutum prothocolli Extractum Magistratualiter Commissionati A. Magistratui hisce off.....referimus per nos peractam in punito verberationis gremiali Judao Herczegh illata hic sum advolutam facti speciem et sub investigationem. Zomborini 8. Avg, 1808.

Nicolaus Simits senator
Georgius Sztrilich senator

Relatio Intuitu verberationis Judao Herczegh illata.

Translation

Specification

The medical care of Jew Lawrence Hertzeg, member of the community, cost this much:

For examination and findings: 2 florins

For 38 physician visits in the period from 19 July to 6 August, where each individual visit cost 36 kreutzers: a total of 20 florins

For necessary medications: 6 florins and 51 kreutzers

Total: 28 florins and 51 kreutzers

Certified in Sombor on 12 August 1808

Josef Oravec, City Surgeon

Specification of costs of medical treatment of Jew Lawrence Hertzeg

Specification of costs and damages of the undersigned

33 silver coins that he had with him, and that he lost on the occasion, worth 66 florins in modern currency

To surgeon for medications: 3 florins and 4 kreutzers

For transportation to Sombor paid to some man: 2 florins

They tore the tunic and returned it in a completely unusable state; its value is 10 florins

For three visits to attorney: 3 florins

To surgeon for medical care and to pharmacy for all medications: 28 florins and 51 kreutzers

To clerk for compiling this specification: 1 florin

Total: 113 florins and 55 kreutzers

Or, if the first item is estimated to only 33 florins: a total of 80 florins and 55 kreutzers

Lawrence Hertzeg, member of the Jewish Community

Certified in Sombor on 12 August 1808

Findings

Upon examining Jew Lawrence Hertzeg, resident of Sombor, on 19 July 1808, I have found that the aforementioned is of the following health condition:

1. On the right side of his face there is a scratch, half a thumb long, probably inflicted by nails.
2. On the left side of the lower part of his jaw his beard has been ripped out.
3. On the right side of his neck there are 6 scratches, with scabs, I suppose inflicted by nails.
4. His left shoulder was dislocated, with two other contusions followed by swelling and scratches two thumbs wide, with injured ligaments.
5. The left side of his collarbone has suffered two contusions.

6. The undermentioned patient has complained that he feels chest pain and has difficulties breathing.

I did not reduce the dislocation of his left shoulder, but I am certain that it had indeed been dislocated, since it was reduced by another surgeon on 17 July.

I humbly present all of this as credible to the honourable Court.

Certified in Sombor on 19 July 1808

Josef Oravec

City of Sombor Surgeon

Findings for Jew Lawrence Hertzeg,

Investigation

The case of the attack and beating suffered by Jew Lawrence Hertzeg, resident of Sombor, on his way to Baja, not far from a winery named *Dakovska*, performed by Nikola and George Fratric, Augustin Rados, and George Jozic, members of the community.

The attack took place on 17 July 1808, and the investigation has been carried out by us, the undersigned.

Firstly, Michael Fratric has stated that on the said day he, together with Nikola and George Fratric, Augustin Rados, and George Jozic, stayed in winery *Djakovska* for amusement, but that he went home earlier, since he had high fever and did not feel well, and therefore did not witness the attack by his friends and acquaintances on Jew Lawrence Hertzeg. However, he knows that Nikola and George Fratrić, in front of him and other witnesses, in the evening of the same day, said the following, 'If you had been there, to see how we ripped out the *Chifutin's* beard!' That is all he knows.

On the other hand, the second witness, Martin Fratric, has stated that, standing close to the scene of the incident, he saw that the Jew, approaching with his wagon, firstly spoke to the attackers, and that then he went off the road, but that they grabbed the wagon by its wheels and tried to overturn it, and that after that they knocked the Jew to the ground, and that Augustin Rados grabbed his beard. That is all he knows.

Facts as they seem so far

Regarding the attack and beating suffered by Jew Lawrence Hertzeg, resident of Sombor, on his way to Baja, not far from a winery named *Djakovska*, performed by Nikola and George Fratric, Augustin Rados, and George Jozic, members of the community, on 17 July 1808.

Lawrence Hertzeg, who was attacked and beaten by Nikola and George Fratric, Avgustin Rados, and George Jozic, officially summoned before the Magistracy, has stated the following: that on 17 July 1808 he was travelling peacefully to a fair in Baja, and that he, not far from winery *Djakovska* saw the four aforementioned men coming back home from the direction of the winery; that they were wearing hoods, that he did not know them by their name, and that he therefore on purpose directed

his wagon off the road – out of decency, and in order to avoid any argument; that they, despite that, were swearing, they grabbed the wagon by its wheels and tried to overturn it; that they pulled him out of the wagon, knocked him to the ground, pulled his clothes, beat him, dislocated his left arm and pulled his beard; that he on the occasion lost 33 silver florins he had with him, and that he was forced to come back to Sombor after the incident.

Protocol excerpt

To the member of the Jewish Community, Lawrence Hertzeg, who has complained that he was attacked and beaten by Nikola and George Fratric, Augustin Rados, and Georgen Jozic on his way to Baja.

It has been decided that gentlemen Senators Nikola Simic and George Sljivic, who already heard the oral statements of the witnesses, in order to be better acquainted with the case, interrogate additional credible witnesses: Matthaeus Jozic, Toma Rados, Marko Fratric, in order to conduct further investigation. In the City of Sombor Senate, on 25 July 1808.

Emerik Bosnjak, City of Sombor Vice Notary

We, the undersigned of the protocol excerpt, hereby inform the much respected Magistracy about the steps we have taken regarding the investigation of the case of beating of Lawrence Hertzeg, member of the Jewish Community, which is still ongoing. In Sombor, on 8 August 1808.

Nikola Simic, Senator

George Sljivic, Senator

Report on the case of beating of Jew Hertzeg,

Rezime

U radu se daje transkript i prevod arhivskog dokumenta, koji se čuva u Istorijskom arhivu Sombora, a koji se odnosi na slučaj prebijanja Lavrentija Hercega, Jevrejina iz Sombora. Ovaj istorijski izvor je važan, jer je slučaj dobro dokumentovan, a osim toga pruža uvid u proceduru koja se sprovodila u takvim situacijama. Dokument sadrži lekarski izveštaj, specifikaciju troškova i izjave svedoka.

References

1. Шосбергер П. Јевреји у Војводини. Кратак преглед историје војвођанских Јевреја [Jews in Vojvodina. A short overview of history of Vojvodina Jews]. Нови Сад: Прометег; 1998.
2. Historical Archive of Sombor, Magistrate of the City of Sombor, 1202/1808

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Reviewed: 13/12/2019

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The scanned copy of the document that is being kept in the Historical archive of Sombor, fund of the Magistrate of the City of Sombor, signature 1202/1808

Specificatio

Cura Chirurgica Iudaei Laurentii Herkey Graec.
„malis inhabitatoris, ut sequitur. - p. „ 2.
1^o Pro Viso Regente. - - - - - 2. „ -
2^o a 14^o Julij usque 6^o Augusti a. c.
38. Visitas ei praestiti, Singulae
Visitae a B. H. Computandae, fauit. 20. „ -
3^o pro Responsis Medicamentis - C. „ 51.
Summa 28. f. „ 54. R.

Sig. Sombor di 12^a Aug. 1808.

Josephus Krausz
Ord. Catenis Chirurgus

[Faint, mostly illegible handwriting on the left side of the page]

[Faint, mostly illegible handwriting on the right side of the page]

Specificatio

Quae Chirurgus dicitur

Laurentii d'Hervey

818 cor. Km

Ich habe die gepflanzte Begräbnis, beinahe aus
den dem Lande, Gräber bei Sember sein
obenan ist nur die Galmesjeth gepflanzte
werden werden. Ich alle alle, jüngst
Jahr die, Gara am 14ten Juli 1878.

Joanitz Hingsteyer
Chirurgus.

Specificum

Expensarum pro Insperaverisptum in cui Curam habitarium, & quidem

Pro ff in Argentea Pecunia penes se habitor. qui percipiunt inmoderato pretio assumpti facti.	60.	x
Pro Chyrurgo pro medicamentis soluti.	3.	4.
Pro Vectura homini cuidam Zombocinum usque soluti.	2.	"
Tunicam brevem ex Gniis laevissimam, & invaluabilem reddiderunt pro qua computat.	10.	"
Pro ternis advocacionibus illius Pluffarioni soluti.	3.	"
Chyrurgo pro cura, & ad Apotecam pro medicamentis soluti.	28.	3.
Candellis pro apposito Specifico soluti.	1.	
	Summa	117. 55.
Provisio t. hinc ad 33/2		33
		80. 55.

Laurentius Hertzegh
denu gelis

Acto Zombori die 12 Augusti
1808.

~~Laurentius Hertzegh~~

Visum Reperitum.

Super Iulio Laurentio Hertzeg Inhabitatore Lomborini,
 "enfi, quem die 19. Julij 1808. in sequente Statu valetudinario
 reperi; ut sequitur.

- 1.^o Dextera pars Faciei lesionem cutaneam unius, et medi
 pollicis longam, probabiliter Unguibus factam passus est.
- 2.^o In sinistra parte Maxilla inferioris depilatio Barba ap.
 "parebat.
- 3.^o In dextera parte Colli sex N^o lesionem cutaneam sanguo.
 "ne suffusa, ita censio unguibus facta reperienda sunt.
- 4.^o Sinister Humerus Luxationem passus est, praeterea duo
 N^o signa Contusionum cum tumore, et decussione Cutis
 duorum pollicum in latitudine, cum Tendinum lesione
 videbantur.
- 5.^o Sinistra Clavicula duo N^o Contusionem accepit.
- 6.^o Supradictas Patiens contra Bectoris dolores, et contra
 gravem respirium mihi conquestus.

Quod luxationem Brachii sinistri ego non recognoverim, de
 eo sum certus veram luxationem Brachii habuisse, quae
 per Chirursum Parensem die 17. Julij recognita est.

Quo fide digno Simplissimo Iudicio Sumillime repero.

Triest. Lomborini die 19. Julij 1808.

Josephus Pravecchio
 M.D. Chirurgus Citijs
 Lomborini

Juden-Lawen der Herrsch.
W. J. von Regensburg

Ad. H. 1202. 808.

Ⓝ

Investigatio.

Primum Aggressionis ac Verberationis, Laurentii Hertzeg
 Iudaei hujati in via Rajam Thurensis, non procul
 a Civica Edificio Polveris dextra, per Nicolaum
 ac Georgium ambos Fratres, nec non Augustinum
 Radom, atq. Georgium Lopez omnes proxime
 Die 17. Julii 1778. Ulata, per nos Inquisita facta.

Primum Michael Fratres fecerit q. quod proxima die
 cum Nicolao et Georgio Fratres, idem Augustino
 Radom, nec non Georgio Lopez in Edificio Civica
 Polveris dextra recreationis causa cum his
 ipis exierunt ad altera domum suam rever-
 ty pergressi, et memento febres semes mala va-
 lere sentiens, pro sui consocij domum ad
 altera abeundo non videns, quod ter eum Com-
 plici Iudaeum Laurentium Hertzeg agredien-
 do verberaverit, aut sibi notum sit, quod ipsi
 die ad vespere et eum consocij duo quippe
 Nicolaum et Georgium Fratres septem abeundo
 Teri sequentis hij formalit. naraverint: Hertz-
 eg; dicit videt, katormo Cifertum fratrem
 Huzgal. de reliquis nihil.

Secundus Martinus Fratres dicit, quod idem a
 loco aggressionis non procul constitutus videns,
 quod ter Iudaeus primus proximit. videlicet
 aggressoris denavit, illi vero eo non obsecra-
 Iudaeum agrediendo, telumq. vobis capiendo
 eundem Iudaeum e telumq. evertere voluerit,
 sic lutando ad terram deprecavit, denique
 Augustinum Radom eundem Iudaeum p. h.
 barbam coepit. De reliquis nihil.
 Tertius

Species-Facti

Intuitu Aggressionis, ac Verberationis, Laurentio Hertzeg
 Natus, geminali, in via Bajam ducente, non procul a
 Civico Ducillo Pakoviensi nuncupato, per Nicolaum,
 et Georgium ambos Fratres, nec non Augustinum
 Rados, atque Georgium Tzoris omnes geminales, die
 17. Julii 1878. illatis, ex quidem:

Laurentio Hertzeg intuitu aggressionis, ac Verbera-
 tionis per Nicolaum ac Georgium Fratres, item Au-
 gustinum Rados, nec non Georgium Tzoris eadem ille-
 to coram Nobis Magistratualiter Commissionarij de-
 dexis, quod eodem die 17. Julii 1878. propria telyiga
 ad mundum Bajenses pacifice profectus, et non
 procul a Civico Ducillo Pakoviensi nuncupato in
 publice via constituto videns praepositos 17.
 4. Inhabitatorum hujatas pro tum sibi de Agnomi-
 nibus ignotos, diripio ludens, ex parte Pako-
 viensi, et ducillo verberat illud rediens, propter
 condensationem ob majorem ini handum baros,
 videndoq ob amorem pacis ipsi sue telyige a pro-
 cul deviaris, illi vero non considerata hacce
 per eundem Tzorem facta deviatione, inter Has-
 ptemias primo rotas telyige capiende telyigam
 invertere, ipsamq Tzorem et telyige epicere
 volueris, subrep te telyige ad terram detertum
 per vestem capiende traxeris, complere, ictus
 corpori eundem intuleris, trahendoq memum ha-
 vom traxeris, mo per barbam eius barbae
 capillorum cum emulsiore coeponis, haicq occu-
 sine dum talites per eodem aggressionis fuisset,
 dum Tzorem penes se habitos in argento Tzoris
 perdidit, atque promineti aggressionis, hu-
 danum, dum illi Lomborum reverti coartus fuisset
 ac redire volueris eadem Querelam deponendi
 gratia, Lomborum redire non admiseris, verum

eundem

ad N 1202 2 858

Extractus Borocotti

№ 1104 Iudeo Promiali Laurentio Horregh et sui per Nicolaum
& Georgium ambos Fratres, nec non Augustinum Radoff
a quo Georgium Iohannem in Via Bajam ducece Preterire
faciam Aggressionem, & Verberationem Querulanti.

Deponsum est:

Domini Senatus Nicolao Simice et Georgio Kisi-
les pro Investigatione Conisus auditis Testibus Oralem
Relationem Testibus siquidem pro Notionem Cruden-
tione plures Testes Authentici forensi maxime est
quidem Orga Fiducioneales Domini Senatus Martia
Kobies, Thome Radoff, Marii Fravius dimissis, ubi
viciorem Vera Investigationem Domini praesentia Sen-
natus Relationem faceris committi. In Senatu
Lombriensi die 25^{ta} July 1808. Celebras.

Extradere per Ordinarium Profugam
Deo Fetti, Notari.

Inscriscripti penes hii sub .j. aduolutum Brothuesii.
I. Etiam Magistratus Commissionarij C.
Magistratui hinc ipse conferimus per nos per
II. tractum in punto verberationi gremiali In.
hoc Obsequio illata hii sub .j. aduolutum.
III. tam facti speciem et sub .j. Inve.
III. stigationem. Lombardi 8^{to} Augi 808.
Nicolaus Smitzberger.
Georgius Strubler Senator

